

TEACHING ENGLISH VIA APPLICATIONS BASED ON THE ANDROID OPERATING SYSTEM

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Abstract:

It is important to note that English is the main language of many spheres: politics, science, information technology, business, education, sports, etc. This explains the desire of society to teach and study it. Today there are different approaches: traditional full-time education, online schools, various options for self-study, and others. This article evaluates the investigation of the English language using modern applications based on the Android operating system.

Key words: online schools; applications based on the Android operating system; content; subscription.

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According to statistical research, in 2021, more than 1.35 billion people spoke English. a person, which is about 17% of the world's population [1]: this fact shows that the role of the English language in the modern world is invaluable.

English is the language of international communication. ED Tech marketplace research shows that English is the official language in 75 different countries of the world (in 55 countries – de jure; in the rest - de facto), which is almost 30% of all countries in the world. It is important to note that some territories of other countries also recognize English as an official language. For comparison, a little more than 500 million people speak Spanish in the world, 270 million people speak French, and about 130 million people speak German. Today, the only language comparable to English in terms of the number of people using it in communication is Chinese, according to various sources, 900 million people to 1.3 billion speak it [2].

To evaluate the effectiveness of this teaching method, the following applications were analyzed: Lingualeo, Duolingo, Busuu, Simpler, Memrise, Ewa, BBC Learning English, and Easy Ten. The article presents the results of the most popular of them: Lingualeo, Duolingo, and EWA.

Duolingo is widely distributed among schoolchildren and students. According to statistics, it is used by more than 150 million people [3]. The learning platform allows you to use a variety of modern techniques for teaching English, starting from traditional reading and ending with games and tasks aimed at developing auditory perception, and expressing your thoughts.

Duolingo supports learning more than just English. In general, the application is free, but it contains the possibility of purchasing additional paid content. An annual family subscription will cost the user more than 10,000 rubles.

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Among the disadvantages of the Duolingo, application are technical problems with download speed, unstable operation, as well as inaccuracies in the translation and pronunciation of individual words and replicas.

Lingualeo is also a sought-after app for learning English. Compared to Duolingo, this application is aimed at children and school audiences. According to Google Play, about 23 million people use this application [4].

An important advantage of Lingualeo is the ability to function without a permanent Internet connection. The main functions of the application are available to users for free, there is an opportunity to purchase additional content. It is possible to get temporary access to a premium account for free, constantly using the application.

Another distinctive feature of the application is the equipment of thematic dictionaries with illustrations, which allows you to improve the memorability of words, phrases, and expressions.

Among the disadvantages of Lingualeo is the application interface. Despite its appearance, pleasant to the eye, it is not intuitive, so it is often very difficult for a child to navigate the functions of the platform. In addition, it is important to note that Lingualeo has a powerful PC version. The smartphone version lacks many of the features available on computers.

For understanding English speech, reading, and writing, the free **Ewa** application is suitable for users. The application is used by more than 40 million people [5]. The training platform contains unique teaching methods: conversational courses, action games, didactic flashcards, and training with the help of viewing films and TV series. The platform is also equipped with a huge library of books in English.

An important advantage of the application is the ability to switch to the dictionary in one click, which allows you to significantly expand your vocabulary and pronounce each word correctly.

The training courses in the application are divided by complexity and topics from introduction to listening, which increases auditory perception. Separate courses are devoted to the study of English slang, which indicates that the application is designed for a wide range of users.

Ewa also contains paid content, including both an annual subscription and individual courses. Among the disadvantages are problems with downloading individual books and a dictionary, as well as the inability of the application to work without an Internet connection.

The comparative characteristics of the considered applications are presented in Table 1.

Comparative Characteristics of popular Applications for learning English

No	Name of the app	Target audience	Number of users, in billions	Merits	Drawbacks
1	2	3	4	5	6
1	Duolingo	- pupils; - students; - adults.	150	-interactive learning system; -exercises for speech development; -orientation to the user with the	-inability to use without an Internet connection; -errors in the translation and pronunciation of

				different initial levels of knowledge.	individual words and phrases; -insufficient optimization.
2	Ewa	- pupils; - students; - adults.	40	Wide range of courses aimed at various aspects of language learning; -real-time translation of words and phrases from the text; -gradation of courses depending on the complexity and tasks of the user.	-inability to use without an Internet connection; -problems with loading the library of books; -insufficient optimization.
3	Lingualeo	- pupils; - kids.	23	-does not require an Internet connection; -availability of dictionaries with associative illustrations; -availability of bonuses for users with constant use of the application.	-most of the content is available only after subscribing; -the application interface is quite complicated to understand; -the mobile version of the app is much inferior to the PC version

Having considered the most popular applications for learning English based on OC Android, it is safe to say that most of them can be divided into two categories: "universal" applications for users with different initial levels of knowledge of the language, and applications aimed at individual groups of users.

Duolingo and **Ewa** applications are suitable for different audiences and are universal. The applications use different teaching methods, but they are practically useless without access to the Internet.

Lingualeo is a vivid example of highly specialized applications aimed at a children's audience

After analyzing applications focused on learning English, it is safe to say that no application will allow you to master the language 100%. On the other hand, apps can be a great addition to traditional approaches.

Applications focused on learning English can significantly simplify the processes of understanding grammar, develop an auditory perception of the language, etc. In other words, if used correctly, they can bring significant benefits. Thus, we consider it reasonable to introduce such applications into the educational process in educational institutions of various levels.

We also consider it appropriate to develop training applications for specialists in narrow specialties of various industries, such as, for example, aviation technicians. Such applications will greatly facilitate the process of learning English in such professions.

In conclusion, it is worth paying attention to optimizing the considered applications for various devices. Such applications should be made as accessible to a wide range of users, increase the list of available free functions, and minimize paid content.

References:

- [1]. *English in numbers. Statistics [Electronic resource] // ENGLISH, SIR.* URL: <https://englishsir.ru/about-english/populyarnost-anglijskogo-yazyka-v-mire-fakty-v-czifrah/>. (Accessed 15.03.2022).
- [2]. *Duolingo: learn languages [Electronic resource] // Google Play.* URL: <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.duolingo&hl=ru&gl=US>. (Accessed 12.03.2022).
- [3]. *Learn English with Lingualeo [Electronic resource] // Google Play.* URL: <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.lingualeo.android&hl=ru&gl=US>. (Accessed 18.03.2022).
- [4]. *EWA: Learn English [Electronic resource] // Google Play.* URL: <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.ewa.ewaapp&hl=ru&gl=U>. (Accessed 16.03.2022).